

DETERMINATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF GENERAL ENDURANCE OF FOOTBALL PLAYERS AGED 15-17

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Abstract. Modern football covers a large number of technical and tactical actions with different structures and degrees of complexity in different variants. In addition to the playing role, the activity of football players and the nature of their actions are influenced by many factors, and the effectiveness of the game depends on the psychophysiological status of the player, which determines his individual characteristics. A football player must have a high level of technical and tactical skill.

Keywords: Football player, endurance, stability, method, sport.

INTRODUCTION

The sports skill of 15-17 year old football players is determined by the following factors: body length, physical performance, complex manifestation of speed, dexterity and technique in specific complex coordination actions. At the same time, the quantitative parameters of competitive activity are determined by these factors by 49.4% ($r = 0.703$), qualitative parameters - by 30.8% ($r = 0.555$).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

General endurance involves the development of all physical qualities, strengthening of the musculoskeletal system, improvement of moral and volitional preparation and the creation of the necessary base of aerobic capabilities. Training the general endurance of football players involves continuous long-term work using a number of methods: repeated-variable, interval and competitive with the mandatory use of physical activity components - duration, intensity, rest intervals, nature of rest, number of repetitions [3, 4].

Proven test exercises for speed and speed endurance can be used for operational monitoring of the special preparedness of players at a certain stage of their preparation for important competitions. A reliable test for determining starting speed is running over a distance of 10 m, which is closely related to the effectiveness of competitive activity (ECA) and can be an objective criterion for selecting players for teams of various sports levels; secondly, based on the data

obtained, it is advisable to use a test exercise for speed endurance to monitor the level of development of speed endurance and functional readiness of athletes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Factors of functional and biochemical economization determine the ratio of the result of performing an exercise and the costs of achieving it. Typically, efficiency is associated with the energy supply of the body during work, and since energy resources in the body are almost always limited, and due to factors that complicate their consumption, the human body strives to perform work at the expense of a minimum of energy consumption. At the same time, the higher the qualification of the athlete, especially in sports that require endurance, the higher the efficiency of the work he performs.

Personal and mental factors have a great influence on the manifestation of endurance, especially in difficult conditions. These include motivation to achieve high results, stability of attitude towards the process and results of long-term activity, as well as such volitional qualities as determination, perseverance, endurance and the ability to tolerate unfavorable changes in the internal environment of the body, to perform work to the limit of one's capabilities.

Factors of genotype (heredity) and environment. General (aerobic) endurance is determined by the influence of hereditary factors (heredity coefficient from 0.4 to 0.8). The genetic factor significantly influences the development of anaerobic capabilities of the body.

Factors in the manifestation of endurance are: the perfection of the processes of aerobic and anaerobic energy supply mechanisms, the level of technical and tactical training, and strong-willed qualities.

Among the physical qualities that are specific and leading for a football player, endurance should be noted. During the research activities, it was established that in the preparatory period the percentage of loads of predominantly aerobic and mixed orientation ranged from 70% to 90%.

In the preparatory period, the percentage of the volumes of training and competitive loads was 94% and 6%, respectively, which indicates an insignificant influence of competitive activity on the preparedness of players at this stage of preparation (table).

Table - Distribution of loads of various primary directions at the stages of the annual cycle in % [4]

Load direction	Stages				
	General preparatory	Specially prepared	Pre-competitive	Competitive	
				1 lap	2 lap
Aerobic	55	44	50	36	40
Aerobic-anaerobic	35	26	38	36	30
Anaerobic	2	8	-	3	3
Competitive	2	10	4	16	21

To achieve success, coordinated actions of all team members are required, subordinating their actions to a common task. The actions of each team player have a specific direction, according to which the football player is distinguished by role. The distribution of players by function is one of the basic principles of gaming activity. Players are distinguished by role not only by their playing techniques and position on the football field, but also by their psychophysiological characteristics.

CONCLUSION

Consequently, the level of physical development and physical fitness of football players aged 15-17 years is determined by the complex influence of morphological, pedagogical, and psychological factors. During the period of the pedagogical experiment, the relative increase in length, body weight, Quetelet index and OGK was 1.6 for young men who were not involved in the sports section; 4.6; 2.5; 2.2%. Thus, among young men attending the football section, it contributes to a more intensive development of endurance, as well as the formation of technical readiness, which will be the key to the formation of competitive activity. One of the determining factors is the direction of training influences, a rational combination of general and special physical training.

The relationship between psychophysiological, psychomotor and socio-psychological indicators with the effectiveness of competitive activity (ECA) of football players of various sports qualifications is determined using correlation analysis. Thus, among the psychomotor indicators at the level of the 2nd category, 1st category, the relationship with ECA has a complex reaction ($r = 0.590$; $r = 0.660$), reaction to a moving object ($r = 0.522$; $r = 0.630$); from psychophysiological ones - distribution and concentration of attention ($r = 0.680$; $r = 0.690$).

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